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**Quiet Quitting:
Is it a Trend Among Metro Manila Professionals?**

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I. INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Have you heard about quiet quitting? Some of you might have heard about it through social media or within your organization. Quiet quitting is the term used when you are not outright quitting your job, but you are quitting the idea of going above and beyond. You are still performing your tasks, but you no longer believe in the hustle culture mentality that work has to be your life (Rosalsky & Selyukh, 2022). People say that there are three versions of your job: first is the one that's on your job description, second is the one you actually do, and lastly is the one that your company expects of you. For the most part, we are happy to go a little beyond what is expected of us, which is the fear of job loss can spur our competitive sides but what doesn't get spoken about enough is when going above and beyond is the expectation (Bakshi, 2022). The quiet quitting trend suggests that employees are increasingly feeling that this exchange has become unbalanced: Employers are demanding additional effort from workers without giving them enough in return. And critically, as the economic outlook worsens and outright quitting becomes less feasible for many people, this quiet alternative is likely to become increasingly common (Klotz & Bolino, 2022).

While much has been written about the Great Resignation, the term "quiet quitting" has emerged to describe an increasingly common alternative to resigning. Driven by many of the same underlying factors as actual resignations, "quiet quitting" refers to opting out of tasks beyond one's assigned duties and/or becoming less psychologically invested in work. Quiet quitters continue to fulfill their primary responsibilities, but they're less willing to engage in activities known as citizenship behaviors: no more staying up late, showing up early, or attending non-mandatory meetings (Klotz & Bolino, 2022). Another article defines quiet quitting as not taking your job too seriously. The phrase is generating millions of views on social media as some young professionals reject the idea of going beyond the limits of their careers, labeling their lesser enthusiasm a form of "quitting." Across generations, U.S. employee engagement is falling, according to survey data from Gallup, but Gen Z and younger millennials, born in 1989 and after, reported the lowest engagement of all during the first quarter at 31% (Ellis & Yang, 2022).

However, while the term "quiet quitting" may be new, the idea behind it has long existed and has been studied under different names as a decades-long phenomenon: disengagement, neglect, and withdrawal. The idea of "quiet quitting" is particularly resonating at the moment because of the COVID-19 pandemic and the increased conversations around mental health. In many instances, employees are taking action to stave off burnout, and that quiet quitting is effectively restoring boundaries to the job description so that people are not thinking about work 24/7. Instead, people are devoting time and energy to other elements of their lives that are more meaningful, leading to improved wellbeing (Christian, 2022).

Objective of the Study

A research study designed to identify the trend of quiet quitting among Metro Manila professionals had the following general and specific objectives:

A. General Objective

To identify and evaluate the quiet quitting factors and behaviors exhibited by affected working employees.

B. Specific Objectives

1. To determine the magnitude of quiet quitters based on age, gender, salary range, years of experience, and industry.
2. To validate which of the three domains are present among professionals who are quiet quitters,
3. And to identify specific factors of quiet quitting that are exhibited in one's professional life.

Scope and Limitations

This study has to acknowledge several limitations. The sample population may not capture the general perception of the wider variety of working professionals in Metro Manila, as we used sampling and online surveys to easily reach the target participants and reduce any difficulty in the data collection constraints. The sample population in this study will only cover the overall professional population based on published 2019 PSA data. It must be acknowledged that statistical approaches were used to provide relationships and correlations among variables. The study was also able to tackle and consider the sample population and any personal or financial issues or constraints, and the data gathered through the survey was heavily relied upon.

The researchers confined the collection of responses of working professionals located only within Metro Manila, Philippines. The target respondents to be surveyed are all professional workers in the National Capital Region belonging to different industries, genders, age groups ranging from 21-30, 31-40, and 41-65 (and up), working experience, length of stay in the current company, and salaries ranging Php0-30999, Php31000-60199, Php61000-90999, Php91000-120999, Php121000-150000, and above the Php150000 bracket.

Further research on the topic and a more comprehensive approach may be incorporated to improve and provide a more specific conclusion and recommendation. Future researchers can benefit from a specific target population to obtain a better picture of the study.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Quiet Quitting Yesterday and Today

There is a similar trend in China known as "tang ping," which began around February 2020 and became popular in May 2021, where young workers are sharing their working experiences (Picoche, 2022). Weibo (2021) described this as a "spiritual movement," whereas Muzaffar (2021) described it as an act of revenge for mankind's pressures to seek jobs and to perform well during lengthy working hours. Young people in this country were already burned out and causing a decline in the labor market due to the culture of hard work in harsh working conditions (Picoche, 2022) with what they thought was a little reward, which emphasized a lifestyle change by "lying flat." Due to its popularity, there are staged photos and memes that elude the country's strict censorship laws (Picoche, 2022), and a social platform group created for this has attracted over 6,000 people (Weibo, 2021).

According to Geertz (1963), the inanity of constant and pointless competition emphasizes involution or the inverse of evolution, and Picoche (2022) relates the phenomenon as a question of obtaining one's own wants in order to be competitive in the workplace. The brutal work condition called "996" was declared illegal by the Chinese supreme court and affects blue-collar workers, logistics professionals, and technological professionals who work from nine in the morning to nine in the evening, six days a week (Yip, 2021), which makes the majority of the Millennials and Generation Z's pursue freelance jobs to escape lengthy working hours (Sun, 2021). By this movement of talent, it became a threat to President Xi jin Ping's "Chinese dream" propaganda (Williams, 2022) which made its citizen slaves without work-life-balance in exchange for "better life" (Siqi, Huifeng, & Peach, 2021).

Gallup's global workplace report for 2022 showed that only 9% of workers in the UK were engaged or enthusiastic about their work, ranking 33rd out of 38 European countries. The NHS staff survey, conducted in the autumn of 2021, showed that morale had fallen from 6.1 out of 10 to 5.8, and staff engagement had dropped from 7.0 to 6.8 (Tapper, 2022).

In the Philippines, there is a term called "Ningas Kugon" that is related to quiet quitting in terms of emotional response but not to the extent of not finishing their tasks. Ningas Kugon is a metaphor for a Filipino character who is eager to get started. According to Carson-Arenas (2004) and Sanchez (1996), there is an eagerness to have speed to reach the climax, but when there is a hurdle and the exuberance stops, the person will end up losing attention and desire, leaving the task undone. And Casuga et. al. (2016) emphasized that it is a shared value that most Filipinos carry related to saying *bahala na*, which means 'to trust God or fate' (Santos, 2020), and the carrier can be anyone; a teenager, an adult, a student, a worker, and so on. Furthermore, Drona (2008) claimed it is the result of an inadequate acknowledgement of the underlying causes that

occurred during development, which leads to a lack of understanding of how to solve it, likely contributing to abandoning the incomplete work to stay away from demotivators.

Quiet Quitting Relating to the COVID-19 Pandemic

COVID-19 fatigue is the case that "people are exposed to chronic stressors as pandemics drag out over many months, and multiple lockdowns wear people down" (Taylor, 2021). The cause of pandemic burnout, COVID-19 fatigue leads to careless behaviors, excessive exhaustion, increased isolation, and a sense of ineffectiveness in life" (Berg, 2021). Moss (2021) listed the leading causes of pandemic fatigue: heavy and uncontrollable workload, lack of control, having no support system, unfairness, and not enough rewards for effort.

The World Health Organization (2019) defines *burnout* as an occupational phenomenon, not a mental health condition and stated that it was "mental exhaustion" which is shallow compared to what the other studies define. They follow the IDC-11 definition which defines *burnout* as "unmanaged workplace stress". Another definition of burnout was stated by Freudenberger (1974) as "going beyond the stressed out feeling of a person" which is an emotional, mental, and physical illness that has a severe impact on a person's health if ignored and downplayed. Marsh (2021) emphasized that burnout occurs in extreme environments where an individual's ability to concentrate suffers, which makes it harder to stay alert and pay attention, and memory and sleep issues arise. Klotz (2022) said that the challenges of remote work during the pandemic are lengthy working hours, remote work stress, uncertainty about returning to the office, and stress and trauma associated with COVID-19 as these factors lead to employee burnout, which leads to much uncertainty and resignation in the USA. Wigert (2020) defined organizational culture as "why we exist," "what we believe in," and "how we do things," which lead to employees' experiences and relationships within the organization, and stated that managers have 70% of the employees' engagement regardless of whether they engage in remote working or not, meaningful interactions must continue to engage with their employees as overworking is usually a suspect for burnout.

Unfortunately, ineffective leaders become the cause of burnout instead of curing it. Unreasonable treatment, setting too far to reach expectations burden the employees and exerting little support to help employees achieve goals (Wigert, 2020). Villarin (2021) pointed out that the impact of the crisis on employees' physical and emotional wellbeing is hardly affected, and many employers predict that it will continue in a post-vaccine environment. Short-term programs to have a band-aid solution to short-term concerns are no longer enough to solve problems. In that situation, companies are now improving their wellness programs to keep up with the changing needs of today's workers.

On Factors Affecting Quiet Quitters

Several factors have been associated with quiet quitting. Workers' **fatigue** has been recognized as a significant problem in the workplace and has been largely associated with high demand jobs, long periods of duties and is a common end result of the combined waking hours, time of day, and level of workload (Haghighi & Yazdi, 2015). Fatigue has also been defined as Fwino not having enough energy to do work and is reluctant to continue or finish a task (Ferrara, 2001). A study conducted by McKinsey & Company revealed that **heavy workloads** are one of the top factors that contributed to the Great Resignation, along with uncaring managers, **inadequate compensation**, and a **lack of career advancement** (Lucas, 2022). McKinsey & Co queried nearly 600 employees and about 35% of the respondents said these three factors were the reasons employees quit. The American Institute of Stress also reported that about 80% of managers and employees feel stressed at work, and excessive workload and long working hours tops the list of leading factors of stressors (Dowd, 2022). In this way, companies tend to lose staff and may find themselves continually hiring and training employees and are stuck in the cycle.

Unhealthy work environment or sometimes referred to as “toxic work environment” refers to a negative work environment where its employees find it difficult to perform their job or advance their careers because of their co-workers, superiors, or the company culture (Dahal, 2022). This environment at the workplace causes emotional, physical, and mental stress and can lead to employee burnout and eventual resignation. Factors such as undefined company core values, no company culture, not enough feedback, and too much focus on the output from a company can create an unhealthy work environment. The largely observed effect in an unhealthy work environment is lack of motivation, poor work-life balance, and that the work no longer excites its employees. (Dahal, 2022)

Effective communication in the workplace is central in reaching company goals and helps its employees to better collaborate and understand each other. However, **poor communication** often creates tense work environments where employees are not motivated to be productive and are not inspired to collaborate at all (Khan, 2021). According to a USC study in 2020, many workers across various jobs feel **underappreciated** especially by their bosses, and that half of the employees say they are thanked only once a week by their supervisors. This creates an atmosphere of missed opportunity in thanking others (Miller, 2020). Being underappreciated can lead to performing poorly and delivering tasks with lack of confidence and drive.

Quiet quitting may also be considered a response to **burnout and stress**, and a way for workers to recover their life (England, 2022). As for job related stress, it can be defined as the harmful physical and emotional responses that occur when the requirements of the job do not match the capabilities, resources, or needs of the employee and can eventually lead to poor health, performance, or even injury (Sauter, et. al., 1999). Some work may be stressful and some

employees are deciding that quiet quitting is the way to go (England, 2022). With regards to COVID-19 pandemic, burnout and stress levels have increased significantly and by January 2022, the American Psychological Association (APA) said that “Burnout and stress are at an all-time high across professions”. A 2021 Indeed study also shows that an increase in burnout is more prominent in younger generations where 53% of millennials already felt burnt-out pre-pandemic which jumped to 59% in 2021 (Madhosingh, 2022).

Work-life balance is defined as being productive at work while also investing equally in one’s personal life (Pandey, 2022). Work-life balance as a factor to quiet quitting may be practiced in several ways such as focusing only on the tasks being assigned, declining to accept work that does not contribute to growth and development, limiting allowed access to work communications outside working hours, making time for family, and many more. According to research, **poor management** is also largely to blame for quiet quitting. Superiors, supervisors, and managers should speak to employees in a meaningful way at least once a week and should discuss goals, recognize good work, and get to know the employees’ strengths and work-life situation to build a good relationship (Nolan, 2022).

III. METHODOLOGY

Questionnaire

The researchers decided to conduct quantitative research in order to identify and evaluate quiet quitting factors and behaviors of affected working employees in Metro Manila. The primary method of data collection will be through an online survey. Based on statistical computation, at least 384 responses should be collected in order to have informed and accurate results from the study.

The questionnaire is composed of 3 major parts: the first part covers the demographics, where respondents will input their name, age, gender, area of expertise, employment type, years of service with the present company, years of working experience, and salary range per month. Second part of the questionnaire covers the three identified domains that are associated with quiet quitting namely reward, environment, and self-fulfillment. Each of these domains cover five questions and a five-point Likert scale will be used to collect data from random respondents. Lastly, the questionnaire contains follow-up questions on quiet quitting awareness, including factors that the respondents thought were associated with them becoming a quiet quitter. A copy of the questionnaire is shown in the appendices.

Data Collection

The researchers chose to conduct an online survey as it is more convenient and efficient. It also renders the survey contactless, protecting both participants and researchers from the COVID-19 virus. The researchers also maximized the power of social media to reach more professionals in the target region. The observers acquired 1,134 impressions via LinkedIn, 8,394 impressions via Twitter, which led to 52 survey clicks from the platform, and also some respondents from the researchers' Facebook posts.

The researchers conducted the online survey from December 3–10, 2022, and received a total of 481 responses. Within the present research, a 5-point Likert scale (ranging from 1 “strongly disagree” to 5 “strongly agree”) was used to rate the professionals’ factors relating to quiet quitting such as reward, environment, and fulfillment.

On its data validation process, 50 of the responses are incomplete; 23 only completed the demographics; and 37 only accomplished the demographics and three domains parts but not the last part. The total number of completed responses is 426. On the other hand, the total professional population of the National Capital Region is 773,362, with 371,214 males (48%) and 402,148 females (52%). The observers used the Cochran method to calculate the ideal sample size

with the desired confidence level and estimated population proportion, which is a minimum of 384 respondents with a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error. To avoid underrepresentation of both genders, the researchers calculated the representations with a minimum of 184 male and 200 female respondents, obtained by autonomously selecting a distinct simple random sample for each population stratum (Mugo, 2002).

Scoring System for Analysis of Data

Based on the data gathered, the researchers decided to create a scoring system in order to determine whether the survey respondent is a quiet quitter based on the qualities mentioned above. The researchers decided to analyze the data per domain and the overall score for a person to be considered a quiet quitter. This is to give a much deeper emphasis on which domain is more common in consideration of quiet quitting and to consider the data as a whole for the person to be a true quiet quitter. In each domain there are a total of five questions and from the Likert scale used, a scoring system of 1 being the lowest and 5 being the highest is used to determine the inclination of the person to the question. The researchers have decided to use a score of 2 per question as a basis for the person answering to be considered a quiet quitter. In total, per domain, the highest possible score for the person to be considered a quiet quitter will be 10. Once the score of per domain reaches a number higher than 10, the person answering is not considered as a quiet quitter. Overall, the highest possible score that a person can achieve to be considered a quiet quitter is 30. Once the overall score reaches 31, the person who answered the survey is not considered a quiet quitter considering the 3 domains.

Ethical Considerations

The research, entitled "*Quiet Quitting: Is it a Trend Among Metro Manila Professionals?*" is bound to identify the factors that define quiet quitting among the working force within the Metropolitan Manila Area which includes business centers such as Makati City, Taguig City, and Quezon City. The researchers are responsible for ensuring that ethical considerations are strictly followed and observed throughout the process. These ethical principles are necessary to practice the utmost respect and guarantee safety before, during, and after conducting the study. Specifically, the researchers shall establish the following considerations:

- Attaining information with honesty and transparency.
- Enhancing research validity through accurate result representation.
- Avoiding any potential harm to the research participants.
- Accessing full and informed consent from the respondents prior to the research.

- Intended for academic purposes only, and researchers agreed that the confidentiality of data would be maintained and protected (data privacy).

IV. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Respondent Demographics

The 426 respondents are divided as follows: Among them, 214 are female (50.2%), 195 are male (45.8%), 11 are nonconforming (2.6%), five people preferred not to respond (1.2%), and one is transgender (0.2%) as shown below in Figure 1.

Figure 1. *Gender Distribution of Respondents*

At the age bracket, 26-30 year olds make up 41% or 173 subjects of the study, followed by 21-25 year olds, who have 120 respondents or 28% of the overall response. Indicating that the majority of the responses are made up of youth because the host country's economic drivers are young (Diokno, 2022). According to PSA, young workers are the 7.3 million portion of 20.14 million national overall working population (Mapa, 2022). The UN International Labor Organization (2020) estimated it to be 20.5 by 2022 and the 20-29 age bracket will be the largest share of the labor market with a median age of 24 years old (Villegas, 2022) compared to neighboring countries like Singapore (Zhang, 2022), South Korea (OECD, 2021; Salmon, 2022) and Japan (Chikiamco, 2022). The age range of 71 respondents, or 17% of the total population, is third in line, with age brackets 36-40 and 41-65 each having 31 (7%) respondents. The distribution of the total number of respondents is identical in the most recent PSA data, which reflects the country's young population.

The top three industries of the survey respondents are from banking and finance (including Fintech) with 91 respondents (21%). Followed by the BPO industry with 57 respondents (13%)

and manufacturing with 42 respondents (10%). However, due to the large number of industries, the researchers decided to group the respondents' industries into four groups. These are primary, secondary, tertiary, and the newest classification, quaternary.

Respondents per Industry

Figure 2. *Number of Respondents per Industry*

According to Britannica (n.d.), the industries are only classified into three segments, primary, secondary, and tertiary. However, quaternary has been added as the fourth element in the group to emphasize technological industries, which are included in emerging work sectors in the country. The first of the industry types is the primary sector; it is the country's economy that produces fundamental materials or energy (University of Cambridge, n.d.).

The sectors that are included in these groups are agriculture and mining. They are the lowest in terms of count which is 10 out of 426 (2%) respondents due to the economy of Metro Manila not being a primary industry location. Next to it is the secondary industry, which is also

considered the manufacturing industry and includes small and large-scale businesses that create goods using raw materials (Oxford University, n.d.). This sector includes respondents from manufacturing, construction, pharmaceuticals, and utilities, which account for 17% of the total survey population. The third industry is tertiary, which has the most representation due to the fact that Metro Manila is a service industry dominated region in which many large corporations and SMEs are located. According to Hayes (2022), this is the biggest industry in the world economy and is defined as the services segment of an economic system, which is further segmented into for-profit and nonprofit sectors.

As manifested by the NCR's economy, the sector received the highest number of responses, 220 (52%) or more than half of the total number of respondents. The industries that has been added to this group are aviation, banking and finance, consultancy, customs, distribution, education, environmental, fashion, finance, fitness, FMCG, trade, government, healthcare, hospitality and tourism, human resources, legal, logistics, manning/manpower, ngo, real estate, publication, recruitment, research, retail and wholesaling, social welfare, and transportation. Due to its large area, an extension has been recognized as the fourth industry group, the quaternary. Britannica (n.d.) emphasized that it is similar to tertiary, that it consists of a combination of both private and public activities. However, it is focused on information-based or knowledge-oriented goods and services. The industries under this category are advertising and marketing, BPO, e-commerce, entertainment and media, information and computer technology, and telecommunications. These industries represented a total of 123 (29%) of the total respondent population, placing them second with the most professionals in the study as shown in Figure 3.

Industry Groups Distribution

Figure 3. *Number of Respondents by Industry Group*

Given that a lot of respondents are young professionals, the majority of participants have three to five years of work experience, which registered 152 respondents (36%). This was followed by five to ten years of experience with 130 (31%), and more than ten years of experience with 99 (23%). The lowest level of experience is one to two years, with 36 respondents (9%), and the highest level is less than a year, with 9 respondents (1%).

Respondent's Working Experience

Figure 4. Number of Respondents by Working Experience

The first three results have more than 50 professionals each in the salary range category. The professionals with salaries ranging from Php 31,000-60,999 have 180 (42%) of the respondents, followed by Php 0-30,999, which has 93 (22%), and Php 61,000-90,999, which has 77 (18%). The other half of the salary range registered fewer than 50 professionals. Php 91,000-120,999 came in fourth with 39 (9%), Php 121,000 and above came in fifth with 22 (5%), and Php 121,000-150,999 came in last with 15 (4%).

Salary Range of the Respondents

Figure 5. Number of Respondents by Salary Range

The study also looked at the relationship between quiet quitting and the length of time spent with the current company. The majority of respondents have zero to five years of experience in their current company, and there is little variation in the numbers within the five year range. Three to five years of service received the most responses in the survey, with 119 (28%), followed by 1-2 years with 111 (26%), and less than a year with 107 (25%). The last two lengths of service are five to ten years old (59%) and more than ten years old (30%).

Figure 6. *Number of Respondents by Years of Service with Current Company*

On the basis of employment type, 90% or 385 out of 426 respondents, work full-time in the private sector, with a significant difference from the second most numerous employment type, full-time professionals in the public sector, which accounts for only 5% or 22 of the total respondents. Following that are the freelancers and the part-time employees, who account for only 3%, 11 of the workers, and the contractual workers, who account for only 8 or 2% of professionals polled.

Employment Type

Figure 7. *Number of Respondents by Employment Type*

Demographic Analysis Based on Domains

Based on the established criteria for quiet quitting, data shows that for each age bracket, there is a dominant domain for which the respondents are considered quiet quitters. Data in Table 1 below shows that for the domain rewards, 71.95% of identified quiet quitters are respondents with ages ranging from 21-30. The researchers also observed that, for the environment, professionals ages 26 to 35 are more dominant. Furthermore, in the domain of self-fulfillment, 45% of quiet quitters belong to the age bracket 26-30. In general, the data shows that more quiet quitters are identified for people with ages 26-30.

Age	<i>Domain Rewards</i>		<i>Domain Environment</i>		<i>Domain Self-Fulfillment</i>		<i>Overall</i>	
	Total	Percentage	Total	Percentage	Total	Percentage	Total	Percentage
21-25	27	32.93%	3	17.65%	2	18.18%	3	30.00%
26-30	32	39.02%	7	41.18%	5	45.45%	5	50.00%
31-35	14	17.07%	4	23.53%	1	9.09%	2	20.00%
36-40	5	6.10%	1	5.88%	1	9.09%	0	0.00%
41-65 (up)	4	4.88%	2	11.76%	2	18.18%	0	0.00%
	82	100.00%	17	100.00%	11	100.00%	10	100.00%

Table 1. *Percentage of Quiet Quitters per Domain by Age*

Based on the data shown for gender in Table 2, the researchers found that female professionals are more likely to become quiet quitters than male professionals. One possible explanation for this would be that females tend to be more sensitive, warm, and emotional

compared to males who are more emotionally stable (Rettner, 2022).

<i>Domain Rewards</i>			<i>Domain Environment</i>		<i>Domain Self-Fulfillment</i>		<i>Overall</i>	
<i>Gender</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Female	51	62.20%	10	58.82%	6	66.67%	6	60.00%
Male	27	32.93%	5	29.41%	3	33.33%	3	30.00%
Non-binary/non-conforming	4	4.88%	2	11.76%	0	0.00%	1	10.00%
	82	100.00%	17	100.00%	9	100.00%	10	100.00%

Table 2. *Percentage of Quiet Quitters per Domain by Gender*

For the salary range, Table 3 shows that respondents with salaries ranging from Php 31,000-60,999 tend to be quiet quitters in all of the domains. It has a percentage of 45.12% for the rewards, 41.18% for the environment and 44.44% for the self fulfillment domain. Followed by professionals who have a salary range of Php 0-30,999, wherein 23.17% tend to quit for rewards, 29.41% for environment and 33.33% for self-fulfillment. Parker and Horowitz (2022) survey finds that low pay was one of the top reasons why people quit. Professionals tend to find a new job that has better pay, more opportunities for advancement, and work-life balance. For the salary ranging from Php 61,000 - 90,999, 17.07% tend to quit for rewards, 11.76% for the environment, and 22.22% for self-fulfillment. Lastly, those professionals who have a salary under the range of Php 91,000 and above are less likely to quiet quit. On the other hand, people who receive a salary of 121, 000 and above tend to quiet quit the least at 2%.

<i>Domain Rewards</i>			<i>Domain Environment</i>		<i>Domain Self-Fulfillment</i>		<i>Overall</i>	
<i>Salary Range</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
0-30,999	19	23.17%	5	29.41%	3	33.33%	2	20.00%
31,000-60,999	37	45.12%	7	41.18%	4	44.44%	3	30.00%
61,000-90,999	14	17.07%	2	11.76%	2	22.22%	3	30.00%
91, 000-120,999	8	9.76%	2	11.76%	0	0.00%	1	10.00%
121,000-150,999	2	2.44%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
151,000 above	2	2.44%	1	5.88%	0	0.00%	1	10.00%
	82	100.00%	17	100.00%	9	100.00%	10	100.00%

Table 3. *Percentage of Quiet Quitters per Domain by Salary Range*

As for years of total working experience, rewards have the highest percentage of quiet quitters with 36.59% as shown in Table 4. These respondents have a total of 3-5 years of working experience. Jones (2019) stated that employees respond positively to any sort of appreciation that comes their way. When their work is valued by others it means their satisfaction rises and productivity increases too. Praise and recognition are fundamental elements in a thriving workplace. As long as people are respected for their efforts and contributions, they will feel a

sense of achievement and keep striving to reach this in every task they undertake. While for the domains of environment and self-fulfillment, the results show that the professionals with years of experience of 5-10 years and beyond 10 years are more likely to quiet quit with percentages tied at 35.29% for environment and 33.33% for self-fulfillment.

<i>Domain Rewards</i>			<i>Domain Environment</i>		<i>Domain Self-Fulfillment</i>		<i>Overall</i>	
<i>Years of working Experience</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
1-2 years	6	7.32%	1	5.88%	1	11.11%	0	0.00%
3-5 years	30	36.59%	3	17.65%	2	22.22%	2	20.00%
5-10 years	22	26.83%	6	35.29%	3	33.33%	5	50.00%
Less than 1 year	1	1.22%	1	5.88%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
More than 10 years	23	28.05%	6	35.29%	3	33.33%	3	30.00%
	82	100.00%	17	100.00%	9	100.00%	10	100.00%

Table 4. *Percentage of Quiet Quitters per Domain by Years of Working Experience*

Lastly, based on the industry of professionals surveyed, we can infer that the tertiary group across all domains is exhibiting quiet quitting behaviors. From the data collected, tertiary group of industries comprise of aviation, banking and finance, consultancy, customs, distribution, education, environmental, fashion, finance, fitness, FMCG, trade, government, healthcare, hospitality and tourism, human resources, legal, logistics, manning/manpower, NGO, real estate, publication, recruitment, research, retail and wholesaling, social welfare, and transportation. The outcome percentage per domain is 63.41% for rewards, 41.18% for environment, and 55.56% for self-fulfillment.

<i>Domain Rewards</i>			<i>Domain Environment</i>		<i>Domain Self-Fulfillment</i>		<i>Overall</i>	
<i>Industry Group</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Primary	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
Secondary	6	7.32%	5	29.41%	1	11.11%	1	10.00%
Tertiary	52	63.41%	7	41.18%	5	55.56%	6	60.00%
Quaternary	24	29.27%	5	29.41%	3	33.33%	3	30.00%
	82	100.00%	17	100.00%	9	100.00%	10	100.00%

Table 5. *Percentage of Quiet Quitters per Domain by Industry Group*

Since the scoring system has already been established, the researchers want to interpret the data to get a better understanding of the results that were gathered. The researchers, in combination with the scoring system, examined the demographic data to find any underlying trends among the people who answered the survey. The demographics used in conjunction with the scoring system are as follows: age, gender, salary range, area of expertise/occupation, years of experience, and industry. This will give the researchers a better view of certain niches that can be

seen from the data which can be used for further studies.

Per Demographic Analysis of Each Domain

Based on the scoring system and the demographics used, the total number of quiet quitters based on the questions used for the domain of rewards is 82 professionals. This means that 19.25% of the 426 respondents to the survey are considered quiet quitters based on their responses to rewards they currently receive or anticipate receiving, such as promotion, additional pay, incentives, recognition, workload adjustment, and teaming up with a close colleague. For the domain of the environment, 17 professionals, or 3.99% of the 426 workers, are quiet quitters who claim that they cannot work efficiently after working hours, that management is unfair and not transparent, that they are afraid or rattle when speaking with their superiors, that their organization does not care about their welfare and growth, and that their organization does not inspire them to perform better. In the final domain, self-fulfillment, only nine respondents, or 2%, are considered quiet quitters who do the bare minimum due to a lack of motivation, purpose, energy, and joy. For the culmination of the quiet quitting traits based on the three mentioned domains, the total number of quiet quitters comes to only 10 or 2.35% of the total number of surveyed professionals in the National Capital Region. An overall score of 30 can be considered too high due to the division of domains, which in turn might not be the case. It is likely that there is one out of the three domains that is bringing the total score of the person down. Another inference here is that only 10 show all three connections with the domains to get a score of 30.

For the rewards domain, there are two items that workers will quiet quit on their work. The absence of recognition of the manager or the organization gained 54% of dissatisfaction among workers. This is due to the nature of employees who want to be recognised for their accomplishments while performing their duties (Syptak et. al., 1999) in which resulting to a greater engagement than those who are not recognized (Littlefield, 2022). The second item is not having a workload adjustment or lessening of task when they were allocated an additional work that got 61% of dissatisfaction among respondents. Professionals' reactions can be attributed to a lack of extra revenue for additional workloads, a dearth of or non-existent support from management, inadequate personal abilities and capabilities, and a lack of time to finish tasks, which can lead to burnout. (Dewi, et. al., 2021) From this, the inference is that the domain of rewards is the domain where people tend to show signs of quiet quitting. The result should be noticed since at least 1 out of 5 people think that they are underpaid, with recognition having the most dissatisfaction, and are considered quiet quitters. Broken down to exact responses, 82 (79%) respondents chose strongly disagree for the statement of being willing to work beyond job description even there is no recognition from the management. It points out their quiet quitting tendencies are manifesting in the absence of acknowledgement and recognition, and also the effort of the organization to prevent them from overworking. It is better for them to be rather strict

with their job description than get no reward, especially when higher ups don't notice the work being done. The least number of respondents with a response of "strongly disagree" is related to colleague rewards, meaning that they're willing to go for the extra mile as long as they are working with a colleague that they like or want. This shows that this is a least likely reason for a person to consider quitting. There are several factors that led the respondents to answer rewards as the most likely domain to exhibit quiet quitting. According to PSA (n.d.), the inflation rate in NCR from Nov 2021 to Nov 2022 increased from 2.2 to 7.5. This in turn made simple goods being priced at a relatively high price. The 10.6 inflation increase in the food sector from 2.3 in 2021 has affected cost of living. Adriano (2022) emphasized the effect of the pandemic, the war between, Ukraine and Russia who are the top producers and exporters of oil, going on outside of the Philippines. This in turn has made the cost of living much higher than in previous years and in turn, affected how goods are to be bought. Another factor that can be stated to influence this is the companies trying to save money by laying off some employees and transferring their work to other countries, with Shopee as one of the examples. According to Royandoyan (2022) Shopee fails to secure funds in the future, it was decided by the organization to layoff employees with redundant job descriptions, majority of the affected workers are with the most of in its customer service department. It then leads to different things like people at the age of 26-30 having a salary range of 31,000 - 61,999, have relatively less experience, and work in a tertiary type of industry. This then creates a persona of a quiet quitter based on the rewards domain. It indicates that the faster-paced environment with a relatively fresh outlook on the corporate world can have a toll on people ages 26-30 which gives them the motivation to think about what they receive.

The domain of environment has a lower percentage of quiet quitters in which focuses on a person's surroundings and how it affects them in relation to staying within the company that they are currently working for. The statement that has a greater response of "strongly disagree" the upper management's fairness and accountability. This data is noticeable because, out of the statements, 17 and 19, respondents who are considered quiet quitters in this domain represent 82% of the respondents. Another observation, the acts of fairness and accountability are more important for the respondents, as these statements indicate the welfare of the employees and making sure that they have a positive mental health in their work environment. The development of the employee plays a role in helping to improve the person's growth. According to Urquhart (2018), 43% of employees resigned due to bad managers, and 53% of professionals switched jobs because of the same reason. As a result, bad managers with no consideration, unfair treatment, not listening to others, and bias have a significant impact on collective performance and the personal well-being of workers (Urquhart, 2018). Lastly, the question with the least number of respondents answering "strongly disagree" is statement 18, relating to the inspiration from their colleagues. The professionals who "strongly disagree" accounted for 18% of the considered quiet quitters in this domain. The researchers do not observe any significant correlation between quiet quitting and inspiration from their co-workers, which states that their colleagues do not give them any reason to be inspired. The quiet quitting persona exemplified here is that the respondents are in the age

bracket of 26–30 years old, with 5–10 years of experience and more than 10 years of experience, with a salary range of Php 31,000–61,999, and in a tertiary type of industry. This creates a unique profile of how the people react to their surroundings and company treatment.

Lastly, for the domain of self-fulfillment, it has the lowest total number of quiet quitters, with only 9 (2%) of the respondents. This focuses on the worker's passion and sense of mission while doing his work. It is the most complex and hardest to articulate when answering the survey, due to the fact that self-fulfillment is not yet experienced by the respondents, which may be attributed to the low score. The statement with the most "strongly disagree" response is "*I have found my purpose with my job and I am filled with joy going to work everyday,*" which indicates that 8 out of the 9 (89%) professionals are considered quiet quitters. This is related to a worker's sense of fulfillment in life, which keeps them doing their work even beyond the limitations of their role, indicating that they are working for their passion and wages are a secondary consideration. As per Burnett (2018), passion does play a factor in choosing what company and job to work for; if a person is not working with passion, this will lead to their dissatisfaction. From the demographics of age, this is supported by the age range with the highest percentage of quiet quitting based on self-fulfillment, the Millennials. On the other hand, the statement in item 22 that they are experiencing fulfillment in helping customers or clients by solving their problems and providing solutions received the fewest "strongly disagree" responses, accounting for 1% of total survey responses. In this domain, the result claims that recognition of others is still a key element when considering quiet quitting in this area.

Recognition of Quiet Quitting

When the researchers asked the participants if they were aware of quiet quitting, 338 (79%) said they were, while 88 (21%) said they were not. The respondents were not asked about the cause of their awareness, but the topic, "quiet quitting," was trending from August 2022 to September 2022, which drew the attention of international and Philippine media organizations, which featured it on their news programs and news articles. It also spread on social media, becoming one of the most popular trending topics on Twitter and TikTok, indicating that the majority of respondents are aware.

Quiet Quitting Awareness of the Respondents

Figure 8. *Quiet Quitting Awareness of the Respondents*

Among the workers who are aware of “quiet quitting,” 189 (56%) of the respondents considered themselves a "quiet quitter" in their workplace, while 148 (54%) think that they are not.

Among the Aware Respondents, Who Considered Themselves as Quiet Quitters

Figure 9. *Among the Aware Respondents, Who Considered Themselves as Quiet Quitters*

Looking at the gender breakdown, female participants have more quiet quitters with 116 (56%) than any other gender group. This is followed by males, which have 84 (40%) and 9 (4%) from others, such as transgender people, non-binaries, and people who did not disclose their

genders. In terms of age range, the 36 to 40 age bracket has the highest percentage of people who consider themselves to be quiet quitters (57%), followed by the 26 to 30 age range (54%), the youngest participants on 21 to 25 years have 53%, the oldest age range of 41 to 65 years has 47%, and the 31 to 35 years bracket has 46%.

The tertiary sector and quaternary groups have the highest percentage of self-considered quiet quitters among industry groups, with 54%. This was followed by the secondary sector (46%), and the primary sector (22%). When it comes to employment types, contractual workers have the highest percentage (71%), yet it is also important to note that they have the fewest numbers among all other groups. This is trailed by full-time professionals in the public sector, who received 62%; full-time employees in the private sector, who obtained 51%; and freelancers, who garnered 46%. Salary ranges from Php 31,000 to 69,999 have the highest percentage (55%) with little variation from other wage ranges. The highest range, Php 151,000 and above, has 54%, followed by Php 61,000 to 90,999 (54%), Php 121,000 to 150,000 (50%), and both Php 91,000 to 120,999 and Php 0 to 30,999 (47%).

For the length of their working experience, individuals with more than ten years of experience have the highest percentage of professionals who claim to be quiet quitters (57%). This was followed by one to two years (53%), three to five years (53%), five to ten years (48%), and less than one year (22%). Lastly for the demographics, the length of stay in their current company, more than ten years of stay, received the highest ranking (66%). Less than a year received 55% of the poll, followed by three to five years (52%), five to ten years (44%), and one to two years (47%).

Aside from quiet quitting awareness and the worker's self-awareness about it, the researchers also asked the respondents if they were counting the working days and looking forward to the weekend. For the excitement of getting a weekend, 358 (84%) of professionals are excited and looking forward to experiencing their weekend or day-offs, while 68 (16%) are not. In terms of quiet quitters, 90% of workers who look forward to spending their weekend day off are quiet quitters, while 76% of non-quiet quitters do as well. Combining these two groups, 55% of respondents are quiet quitters who look forward to weekends or their time off from work.

Professionals Who Look Forward to Their Weekends / Day-Offs

Figure 10. *Percentage of Quiet Quitters Among Professionals Who Look Forward to Their Day-Offs*

The researchers also asked the participants if they looked forward to finishing their work and leaving their workplace on time. This also received a significant number of "yes," with 83%, while those who are not looking forward to it have 17%. In terms of quiet quitters, 84% of self-identified quiet quitters say they always look forward to leaving their offices on time, while 16% do not. On the other hand, the majority of self-aware non-quiet quitters (81%), are also looking forward to leaving their office on time. Overall, when these two professional groups are combined, 53% of professionals who look forward to leaving their office on time are self-proclaimed quiet quitters.

Workers Who Look Forward to Leave Their Office On-Time

Figure 11. *Percentage of Quiet Quitters Among Workers Who Look Forward to Leave Their Office On-Time*

Aside from asking professionals if they anticipate leaving their workplace on time, the researchers also inquired about the factors that caused them to stay in the office past their working hours. 68% of professionals who do not want to extend their working hours claim that their workload forces them to stay past their working hours, causing them to perform below-par. On the other hand, 54% of workers claimed that deadlines force them to stay in the office and work past their contracted hours because they have urgent work to complete. For non-work related factors, avoiding traffic or extreme commuting due to the intense transportation situation of Metro Manila got 30% and chatters between the employees got 29%. Additional pay accounted for 13% of the factors influencing working beyond normal hours due to the reward or additional penny that it can provide to their wages. Finally, other factors such as meetings, a fear of being judged if they went out early, a lack of manpower, and other work-related factors attributed for 5% of the factors.

Factors that Made Respondents Stay Beyond Working Hours

Figure 12. *Factors that Made Respondents Stay Beyond Working Hours*

Factors Affecting Quiet Quitters

The researchers wanted to further understand the factors that likely affected quiet quitters in the survey. Based on the responses, there are 13 factors considered to affect professionals. That includes fatigue, heavy workload, unhealthy work environment, limited opportunities, poor communication, undervalued and underappreciated, underpaid, stress and anxiety, work-life balance realization, COVID-19 pandemic, poor management, burnout, outside work commitments, and errands.

Respondents were allowed to select more than one of the 13 factors, and the results are shown in Table 6. Among the given options, work-life balance realization scored the highest with 39% of the votes. The respondents choose to be productive at their work while also equally investing in their personal lives. They also tend to focus on the tasks being assigned and decline to accept work outside of official work hours in order to make time for personal matters. The second highest voted factor affecting quiet quitters is stress and anxiety, accounting 38% of the responses. Working professionals are now more mindful of their overall health and well-being and try to avoid as much work related stress and anxiety as possible. With 36.15% of the votes, being underpaid is the third most popular factor. Working professionals have been compelled to work within the parameters of their job descriptions, rather than going above and beyond what is expected of management. Underpaying employees demotivates them and discourages them from going above and beyond their assigned duties. This reduces companies' motivation to give them a raise while also treating them unfairly.

The following are the respondents' fourth-to-thirteenth ranked factors: Burnout had 34%, undervalued and underappreciated had also 34%, fatigue had also 34%, heavy workload had 31%, limited opportunities had 30%, unhealthy work environment had 29%, poor management had 27%, poor communication had 11%, and COVID-19 had 10%.

Factors	Votes	Percentage
<i>Work-life balance realization</i>	164	38.50%
<i>Stress and Anxiety</i>	162	38.03%
<i>Underpaid</i>	154	36.15%
<i>Burnout</i>	146	34.27%
<i>Undervalued and unappreciated</i>	145	34.04%
<i>Fatigue</i>	143	33.57%
<i>Heavy workload</i>	132	30.99%
<i>Limited opportunities</i>	127	29.81%
<i>Unhealthy work environment</i>	122	28.64%
<i>Poor management</i>	116	27.23%
<i>Poor communication</i>	47	11.03%
<i>Outside work commitments and errands</i>	47	11.03%
<i>COVID-19 pandemic</i>	42	9.86%

Table 6. *Percentage of Chosen Factors Affecting Quiet Quitters*

Each of these factors was classified by the researchers into domains (Self-fulfillment, Environment, and Rewards). Table 7 shows that despite having only three factors in the Domain of Rewards, it received a large number of votes. As reasons for being a quiet quitter, these factors include being underpaid, undervalued, and having limited opportunities.

Factors	Votes
Domain: Self-fulfillment	
<i>Work-life balance realization</i>	164
<i>Outside work commitments and errands</i>	47
Total Votes:	211
Domain: Environment	
<i>Stress and Anxiety</i>	162
<i>Burnout</i>	146
<i>Fatigue</i>	143
<i>Heavy workload</i>	132
<i>Unhealthy work environment</i>	122
<i>Poor management</i>	116
<i>Poor communication</i>	47
<i>COVID-19 pandemic</i>	42
Total Votes:	910
Domain: Reward	
<i>Underpaid</i>	154
<i>Undervalued and unappreciated</i>	145
<i>Limited opportunities</i>	127
Total Votes:	426

are

Table 7. *Categorized Factors by Domain of Self-fulfillment, Environment, and Reward*

Aside from the 13 factors listed by the researchers, respondents were given the option to add their own factors that they believed were affecting them as quiet quitters. The survey received a variety of personal responses, such as the current economic situation and outlook, demeaning words shared by officemates, doing the bare minimum, going the extra mile, group thinking, insecure colleagues and managers, micromanagement, mental health, motherhood, no motivation, no purpose, no challenge at work, overtime, transportation, and inability to travel. These factors are also thought to be triggers for quiet quitting, accounting for only 4% of the professionals surveyed.

V. CONCLUSION

According to the researchers' findings, there are currently few studies related to quiet quitting. The results show that professionals in the NCR quit quietly. It may have a low rate when the combined three domains are considered, but when recognized per domain, it is shown to be more common. When it comes to rewards, one out of every five respondents considers themselves to be quiet quitters, indicating that it is the primary drive among Metro Manila professionals. It is themselves, and having a great time. This could be one of the main reasons why this is the persona of the person with quiet quitting tendencies in the rewards domain. Aside from that, this can be thought to be due to the country's economic situation, where inflation is at a peak, basic goods are already comparable to the minimum wage, rising oil prices, costlier fares, and other economic factors that make every worker demand a higher salary. Similar to the domain of self-fulfillment, it appears that younger and less experienced people have more doubts about what they want to do, which leads to quiet quitting behaviors. At this age, young professionals are searching for what they truly want in life at this age, which can have an impact on their performance. It also demonstrates that people revert to their natural instinct, which is survival of the fittest. Money is what allows people to live better lives; without it, they would struggle to survive, leading them to assess whether they are being paid adequately.

While the two other domains have similar results and profiles, the domain of environment is still to be considered in terms of how companies treat people and how people are hard on themselves. Similarly, the results came out with the ages 26-30 having the highest number in the domain of environment. There is one exception to how people with much more experience feel about this specific domain. People with more experience have doubts about their career path and company culture, which has significantly influenced how they perceive companies. Their level of experience in the corporate world has changed their perception of companies. Tenured professionals are more aware of how a company handles problems and treats its employees. This informs them about which environments are unsuitable for them to work in. Because these experienced people have families, they do not want to add more stress to their lives and would rather leave than put their heads down when criticised or when their efforts are not recognised. Industry groups also play a role in the manifestation of quiet quitting, particularly in the environmental domain. Since the majority of the companies in the NCR are either tertiary or quaternary, this demonstrates the type of company culture and environment they have.

Another reason why these figures are only 2% of the total respondents is that Filipinos value resiliency. Resilience is the ability to withstand difficult situations and events without giving up or being able to get back on their feet even when there is a lot going on. In relation to this, another trait associated with a low percentage is adaptability. Adaptability is the ability to adjust to different situations, even if they are uncomfortable. Hard-working, a common trait by Filipinos and Carabao, along with resiliency and adaptability, are linked to Filipinos' sense of

responsibility to their families. Filipinos have a tendency to ignore their own stress and tiredness if it is for the benefit of themselves and their families. They would rather work and not complain in order to provide for their families. Their moral values are also evident in their actions, and rather than complaining about what they receive in terms of rewards, treatment from their employers, and colleagues, they simply work hard to achieve what they require.

This also helps to understand some of the bosses who are either data-driven or emotionally invested in their employees. Some managers are only concerned with their employees' output and not with how they are feeling at any given time. This study can assist them in understanding the balance required to retain their employees. This can also aid organizations in comprehending why some employees abruptly resign. The impact of this study can help increase employee retention, and with many people having problems with their jobs, this can provide them with valuable feedback.

However, it is important to note that some professionals do not consider their behaviour to be quiet quitting because they can do exactly what they are told to do with no complaints. There is a common misconception that working for what you are paid for and being a quiet quitter are synonymous. As one of our respondents mentioned, they believe that working only for what you are paid for is not a bad thing and does not necessarily indicate that a person is quietly quitting. Workers may appear to want to work at their own pace, focus on what they need to do, and prioritize other things they think important.

Quiet quitting has become increasingly popular term as public awareness of mental health has grown over the years. People give themselves more time to try to understand what is going on around them and how it will affect them. As a result, mental and emotional exhaustion related to their job became popular as reasons for quiet quitting behaviour. The factors influencing quiet quitting demonstrate how mental instability can impair a person's productivity at work.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS

Other factors, such as establishing a proper domain for quiet quitting, must also be considered. The findings indicate that majority of the professionals in the National Capital Region are aware of the concept of quitting. They may know it by another name or as a result of a combination of factors that led to a person being labelled as a quiet quitter. Certain conditions must be met before considering themselves as quiet quitters, but it needs a concrete definition to fully identify themselves.

There has to be a better way of connecting with individuals in Metro Manila to get better data on who the quiet quitters are. Possibly providing them with a better understanding of what quiet quitting entails will cause them to reconsider if they are quiet quitters. Another lens to consider is qualitative analysis. This can provide more personalized and deeper information about why participants believe they are or are not quiet quitters. This gives future researchers a better understanding of why they think the way they do. This can be caused by a negative work experience, a low-paying job, unfair treatment by a coworker or boss, or a career path that is unclear. A combination of qualitative and quantitative analysis may provide more information. This provides the researchers with a better understanding of the specific factors that can lead to quiet quitting.

Future researchers can focus on the persona developed from this study for more in-depth analysis. Because three domains were used, three personas were created. This can be researched further to see if the personas in this study are correct. Another way to employ personas is on a basis. The personas developed can be used as a foundation for future research related to this survey. They can set the standard for what a quiet quitter is, but they can also be the unusual one out when it comes to determining which other generations are more likely to exhibit quiet quitting tendencies.

A domain reassessment is also advised. Other than the domains mentioned in this study, there may be a better version of the realms. Responses to the factors influencing quiet quitting can be used to help identify domains. There may be redundant or similar answers, but they can be grouped much better to form the domain. Work-life balance is not fully included in the domains established, as evidenced by the data. Stress and burnout can also be classified as one of the three domains. Creating a domain by focusing on what the respondents are feeling is another option. A domain based on physical, mental, and emotional exhaustion, a domain based on how they perceive their salary, a domain based on how they perceive the company for which they work, and a domain based on how they perceive themselves and their career path. All of these domains were created from factors affecting quiet quitting; this can result in a better understanding of what the respondents perceive, giving future researchers an idea of what the ideal work thought is for an individual. Domain-specific questions can also be more defined and specific. There is no need to

compel certain items that are not a possible cause of a quiet quit. The questions can also be simplified to focus on the domain and lead to a more direct assessment. The asking of why based on the questions can be difficult to execute, but it can provide insight into what the respondents will be doing in the future. This, in turn, can provide experts with a better understanding of how to define the meaning of "quiet quitting."

Furthermore, a deeper dive into industry groups can provide a better understanding of which of these industry groups exhibits the most quiet quitting claims. Tertiary industry groups can be one focus because NCR professionals are mostly employed in this type of industry group. A deeper examination of company culture and environment can provide a better understanding of why employees quietly quit. Trends to consider include how fast-paced the environment is, an average analysis of how much overtime an employee renders per month, and trends in which weeks of the month employees typically render overtime. Perhaps a survey by industry can provide a more accurate picture of what the company exhibits. Based on the data gathered by the researchers, quaternary industry groups are also worth investigating. This industry group is known for producing the most stressful work. Communicating with international clients, dealing with technology malfunctions, and so on can be extremely difficult for employees in that industry group, leading to increased stress. This industry group has tighter work schedules and more deadlines that must be met or else they will lose their clients. A deep dive into the company's structure and work KPIs can be a focus to see if these items lead to quiet quitting.

Future researchers can look into a focus on per industry analysis based on the industry group focus of evaluation. According to some of the researchers' assumptions, the BPO, call centre industry would have one of the highest rates of quiet quitting. However, it cannot be carried out because there is insufficient data to determine the true population of BPO employees. BPOs typically handle more stressful jobs because their primary function is to communicate with angry or irritated customers. BPOs are also subject to stricter guidelines regarding what they can and cannot do during working hours. When it's their shift, they appear to be glued to their chairs, which can lead to increased fatigue and stress. As a result, they may seek other avenues for release or simply quit their jobs. This is also a good lens to look at because BPOs have high payouts and can focus on the other two domains to see if these factors are enough for them to quit their job.

Due to the definition of the various generation gaps, age can be a focus for future research. Some characteristics displayed by different age generations may result in different analyses. These people, like the Millennials and Generation Z, tend to be the centre of quiet quitting, as evidenced by their traits. This study will provide a better understanding of why these generations feel this way, as well as how to deal with them. These generations are more emotional and reward-driven, which can be mitigated by companies when hiring and retaining these professionals. Another age group to consider is Generation X or Y. These generations are not

typically the exhibitors of quiet quitting tendencies, and the reasons for this can be investigated. There are some reasons why they do not have problems with their coworkers or companies, and it is important to note these. These can help specific generations understand the concept of quiet quitting without making it too general.

A different focus can be implemented to encourage quiet quitting. The next focus to further enhance and explain this study could be a person's coping mechanisms. People have ways of dealing with the stress of work and personal problems, but there has been little research into the most effective ways of dealing with stress. It may not have been emphasised in this study, but it could be in a future study to determine the effectiveness of coping mechanisms. Coping mechanisms can have various health consequences, and finding the least taxing and most effective way of coping with quiet quitting could be the focus of that study. This can result in medical professionals being better equipped and knowledgeable of what is going on with the patient they are caring for. This can also benefit a doctor's approach to a patient. A better understanding of a patient's situation can provide a more accurate picture of why the patient is sick.

From the perspective of an employer, the recommendation that can be made to improve their treatment of employees is to enquire more about their feelings and status. Companies, in collaboration with their HR partners, can conduct monthly or weekly check-ins to determine employees' true standing. Employees do not say much if they are not asked. HR should implement a strategy that ensures confidentiality of information and anonymity of employee comments. This will give employees more freedom to express themselves. Companies can also have their own psychologist on hand for employees to talk to in order to express how they feel. This can make employees feel more at ease. Because most data shows that employees between the ages of 21 and 30 have the most difficulty quitting quietly, they can adjust their strategies to retain these employees in relation to their ages. Perhaps this age group is more likely to quit quietly because there is no proper mentorship, job description, or they are new to the corporate world. A better introduction to the company can be used to demonstrate to employees that the company values them. Implementation of knowledge transfer policies can be used to set expectations for new company hires with pre-existing job descriptions. They can be given a company tour and hands-on field work to help them understand better. A breakdown of their employee benefits and rewards to be written down as proof of compliance and to avoid any misunderstandings about how they are treated. Because the study's main domain is rewards, this could be the focus of the improvement. This can lead to companies rethinking how they budget employee salaries and internal company movement. Some businesses use budgeting strategies when hiring new employees, and these benefit packages may not be up to date with the current situation in the Philippines. They can assess the market and adjust to the industry average. Internal mobility can be used to address the domain of self-actualization. Some companies offer such opportunities, but if an employee wants to try a specific job and the company cannot provide it, the employee will leave. Internal mobility has been one of the benefits of some companies, and it can encourage

employees to stay longer, resulting in higher retention. Checking KPIs and deadlines can help reduce stress, and HR can use similar studies to determine the breaking point of employees in order to mitigate any burnout or stress they experience.

VII. REFERENCES

- Adriano, F. D. (2022, December 16). What is causing our high inflation? The Manila Times. <https://www.manilatimes.net/2022/12/16/business/top-business/what-is-causing-our-high-inflation/1870491>
- Avelino, S. E., & Sanchez, C. A. (1996). *Personality Development and Human Relations*. Google Books. Retrieved November 26, 2022, from <https://books.google.com.ph/books?id=2oBX1DRwhgsC&printsec=frontcover#v=onepage&q&f=false>
- Bakshi, P. (2022, August 9). In defence of 'Quiet quitting' your job. Refinery29. <https://www.refinery29.com/en-gb/quiet-quitting-job>
- Berg, S. (2021, January 29). *What doctors wish patients knew about pandemic fatigue*. American Medical Association. Retrieved March 7, 2022, from <https://www.ama-assn.org/delivering-care/public-health/what-doctors-wish-patients-knew-about-pandemic-fatigue>
- Burnett, J. (2018, January 10). Millennials want passion more than money at work. Ladders | Business News & Career Advice. <https://www.theladders.com/career-advice/survey-millennials-want-passion-more-than-money>
- Carson-Arenas, A. (2004). *Introduction to Psychology*. Google. Retrieved November 26, 2022, from https://books.google.com.hk/books/about/Introduction_to_Psychology.html?id=S5rVAAAACAAJ&redir_esc=y
- Casuga, S. M., Vogel, E. B., & Pope-Rhodus, A. (2017). *A qualitative content analysis of the Bahala na attitude in Filipino elite athletes*. International Journal of Sport Psychology. Retrieved November 20, 2022, from <http://www.ijsp-online.com/abstract/view/48/419>
- Chikiamco, C. V. (2022, December 25). *Toward a Japan-focused foreign policy*. BusinessWorld Online. Retrieved December 26, 2022, from <https://www.bworldonline.com/opinion/2022/12/25/495034/toward-a-japan-focused-foreign-policy/>
- Christian, A. (2022). *Why 'quiet quitting' is nothing new*. <https://www.bbc.com/worklife/article/20220825-why-quiet-quitting-is-nothing-new>
- Constante, A. (2022, March 17). *How 'hiya,' 'Kapwa' and other cultural values play a role in Filipino American Mental Health*. Los Angeles Times. Retrieved December 10, 2022, from <https://www.latimes.com/lifestyle/story/2022-03-17/how-hiya-kapwa-and-other-cultural-values-play-a-role-in-filipino-american-mental-health>
- Dahal, B. 2022. Effects of Working in an Unhealthy Work Environment. <https://timetracko.com/blog/effects-of-unhealthy-work-environment/>

- Dewi, S. P., Susanti, M., Suffiati, & Cokki. (2021). Effect of work overload on job satisfaction through burnout. *Jurnal Manajemen*, 25(1).<https://doi.org/10.24912/jm.v25i1.703>
- Diokno, B. (2022, June 1). *Diokno touts 'promising economy' to investors*. BusinessWorld Online. Retrieved November 26, 2022, from <https://www.bworldonline.com/economy/2022/06/01/452359/diokno-touts-promising-economy-to-investors/>
- Drona, B. M. (2008, January 12). *Our Filipino norm of Morality*. THE FILIPINO MIND. Retrieved November 26, 2022, from <https://www.thefilipinomind.com/2008/01/our-filipino-norm-of-morality-revisited.html>
- Dowd, M. 2020. Negative Effects of Heavy Workload. <https://work.chron.com/negative-effects-heavy-workload-10097.html>
- Ellis, L., Yang, A. (2022). *If Your Co-Workers Are 'Quiet Quitting,' Here's What That Means*. <https://www.wsj.com/articles/if-your-gen-z-co-workers-are-quiet-quitting-heres-what-that-means-116602>
- Encyclopædia Britannica, inc. (n.d.). *Industry*. Encyclopædia Britannica. Retrieved January 8, 2023, from <https://www.britannica.com/technology/industry>
- Encyclopædia Britannica, inc. (n.d.). *Types of Industry*. Encyclopædia Britannica. Retrieved January 8, 2023, from <https://www.britannica.com/explore/savingearth/industry>
- England, A. 2022. People are quiet quitting and it could be great for our health. <https://www.verywellmind.com/how-quiet-quitting-can-affect-our-mental-health-6502057>
- Ferrara, M., De Gennaro, L., 2021. How much sleep do we need? *Sleep Med Rev*. 5:155–79.
- Freudenberger, H. J. (1974). *Staff Burn-out*. Wiley Online Library. Retrieved November 28, 2022, from <https://spssi.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/j.1540-4560.1974.tb00706.x>
- Geertz, C. (1963). *Agricultural Involution: The Processes of Ecological Change in Indonesia*. Monoskop. Published for the Association of Asian Studies by University of California Press. Retrieved November 27, 2022, from https://monoskop.org/images/8/82/Geertz_Clifford_Agricultural_involution_the_processes_of_ecological_change_in_indonesia_1963.pdf.
- Haghighi, K. and Yazdi, Z., 2015. Fatigue management in the workplace. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4525425/>
- Hayes, A. (2022, January 7). *What are tertiary sectors?*. Investopedia. Retrieved January 8, 2023, from <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/t/tertiaryindustry.asp>
- Jones, M. (2022, June 27). *Why is employee reward and recognition important?* (2022 updated) | Petaurum HR. Petaurum Solutions. <https://petaurumsolutions.co.uk/blog/why-are-employee-rewards-and-recognition-so-important/>
- Khan, H. 2021. The Causes and Effects of Poor Communication in the Workplace. <https://www.simpplr.com/blog/2021/causes-effects-poor-communication-workplace/#:~:text=Poor%20communication%20often%20creates%20a,negatively%20affecting%20the%20bottom%20line>

- Klotz, A., Bolino, M. (2022). *When Quiet Quitting Is Worse Than the Real Thing*.
<https://hbr.org/2022/09/when-quiet-quitting-is-worse-than-the-real-thin60608>
- Lasquety-Reyes, J. (n.d.). *In Defense of Hiya as a Filipino Virtue*. Taylor and Francis. Retrieved December 9, 2022, from
<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/09552367.2015.1136203>
- Li, D. (2021, October 30). *China's 996 work culture is labour exploitation by another name*. South China Morning Post. Retrieved November 27, 2022, from
<https://www.scmp.com/comment/letters/article/3154115/chinas-996-work-culture-labour-exploitation-another-name>
- Lucas, E. 2022. Employees say Unsustainable Workloads and Expectations are Driving them to Quit.
<https://www.forbes.com/sites/emmylucas/2022/03/09/employees-say-unsustainable-workloads-and-expectations-are-driving-them-to-quit/?sh=49c1f9217c34>
- Madhosingh, S. 2022. Employers should fear the truth behind quiet quitting.
<https://www.entrepreneur.com/leadership/employers-should-fear-the-truth-behind-quiet-quitting/435347>
- Mapa, D. S. (2022, July 7). *Employment Rate in May 2022 is Estimated at 94.0 Percent*. Philippine Statistics Authority. Retrieved December 26, 2022, from
<https://psa.gov.ph/statistics/survey/labor-and-employment/labor-force-survey/title/Employment%20Rate%20in%20May%202022%20is%20Estimated%20at%2094.0%20Percent>
- Marsh, S. (2021, February 5). *'pandemic burnout' on rise as latest Covid Lockdowns take toll*. The Guardian. Retrieved November 26, 2022, from
<https://www.theguardian.com/society/2021/feb/05/pandemic-burnout-rise-uk-latest-covid-lockdowns-take-toll>
- Merkielle, GT. (2022) *Cultural Analysis on the Ningas Kugon Value of the Filipinos*.
<https://pdfcoffee.com/cultural-analysis-on-the-ningas-kugon-value-of-the-filipinosdocx-pdf-free.html>
- Miller, J. 2020. A USC study reveals many workers feel under appreciated by bosses and would like a 'thank you' more often.
<https://pressroom.usc.edu/a-usc-study-reveals-many-workers-feel-underappreciated-by-bosses-and-would-like-a-thank-you-more-often/>
- Moss, J. (2021, December 22). *Beyond burned out*. Harvard Business Review. Retrieved April 17, 2022, from <https://hbr.org/2021/02/beyond-burned-out>
- Mugo, F. (n.d.). *Sampling in Research*. University of Nairobi. Retrieved December 11, 2022, from
<http://erepository.uonbi.ac.ke/bitstream/handle/11295/54895/mugo02sampling.pdf>
- Muzaffar, M. (2021, June 9). *Disenchanted young Chinese are 'lying flat' to protest work and Hustle Culture*. The Independent. Retrieved November 28, 2022, from
<https://www.independent.co.uk/asia/china/china-tang-ping-trend-work-culture-b1862444.html>
- Nolan, B. 2022. Half of US workers have "quiet quit" and managers are to blame, according to new study.

- <https://www.businessinsider.com/quiet-quitting-nothing-new-bad-managers-blame-study-d-isengagEd-workers-2022-9>
- OECD. (2021, October 25). *Achieving better jobs, health and opportunities for all*. OECD. Retrieved December 26, 2022, from <https://www.oecd.org/country/korea/thematic-focus/achieving-better-jobs-health-and-opportunitie-for-all-3a1c3641/>
- Pandey, S. 2022. Quiet quitting: The need to maintain work-life balance. <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/blogs/voices/quiet-quitting-the-need-to-maintain-work-life-balance/>
- Parker, K., & Horowitz, J. (2022, March 10). *Majority of workers who quit a job in 2021 cite low pay, no opportunities for advancement, feeling disrespected*. Pew Research Center. <https://www.pewresearch.org/fact-tank/2022/03/09/majority-of-workers-who-quit-a-job-in-2021-cite-low-pay-no-opportunities-for-advancement-feeling-disrespected/>
- Picoche, A. (2022, November 14). *Tang Ping: The Chinese Millennials Lying Flat to protest against overwork: Welcome to the jungle*. Tang ping: Chinese workers lying flat to protest against overwork. Retrieved November 26, 2022, from <https://www.welcometothejungle.com/fr/articles/tang-ping-chinese-milennials-protest-overwork>
- Philippine Statistics Authority. (n.d.). *Summary inflation report consumer price index (2018=100): November 2022 | Philippine Statistics Authority (2022-489)*. <https://psa.gov.ph/statistics/survey/price/summary-inflation-report-consumer-price-index-2018100-november-2022>
- Rettner, Rachael. (2022, October 14). *Men's and Women's Personalities: Worlds Apart, or Not So Different?*<https://www.livescience.com/36066-men-women-personality-differences.html#:~:text=Men%20tend%20to%20be%20more,and%20apprehensive%2C%20the%20study%20found.>
- Rosalsky, G., & Selyukh, A. (2022, September 13). The economics behind 'quiet quitting' — and what we should call it instead. NPR.org. <https://www.npr.org/sections/money/2022/09/13/1122059402/the-economics-behind-quiet-quitting-and-what-we-should-call-it-instead>
- Royandoyan, R. (2022, October 6). *Tales of confusion and budget cuts: Inside Shopee Philippines' layoffs*. *Philstar.com*. <https://www.philstar.com/business/2022/10/06/2214475/tales-confusion-and-budget-cuts-inside-shopee-philippines-layoffs>
- Salmon, A. (2022, December 10). *Demographic time bomb ticking down on South Korea*. Asia Times. Retrieved December 26, 2022, from <https://asiatimes.com/2022/11/demographic-time-bomb-ticking-down-on-south-korea/>
- Santos, A. (2020, December 7). *How your Filipino values can affect your mental health*. SBS Language. Retrieved November 26, 2022, from <https://www.sbs.com.au/language/filipino/en/podcast-episode/how-your-filipino-values-ca>

- n-affect-your-mental-health/oft530wak
- Sauter, S. et. al. 1999. STRESS....At Work.
<https://www.cdc.gov/niosh/docs/99-101/default.html#:~:text=done%20about%20it-,What%20Is%20Job%20Stress%3F,poor%20health%20and%20even%20injury.>
- Siqi, J., Huifeng, H., & Peach, B. (2021, December 23). *What is 'lying flat', and why are Chinese officials standing up to it?* South China Morning Post. Retrieved November 28, 2022, from <https://www.scmp.com/economy/china-economy/article/3153362/what-lying-flat-and-why-are-chinese-officials-standing-it?module=inline&pgtype=article>
- Sun, L. (2021, October 22). *Is China's version of the 'great resignation' creating an army of freelancers?* South China Morning Post. Retrieved November 28, 2022, from https://www.scmp.com/economy/china-economy/article/3152487/chinas-great-resignation-freelancers-find-both-hope-and?module=hard_link&pgtype=article
- Syptak, J. M., Marsland, D. W., & Ulmer, D. (1999, September 30). *Job satisfaction: Putting theory into practice.* Family Practice Management. Retrieved January 20, 2023, from <https://www.aafp.org/pubs/fpm/issues/1999/1000/p26.html>
- Tapper, J. (2022). *Quiet quitting: why doing the bare minimum at work has gone global.* <https://www.theguardian.com/money/2022/aug/06/quiet-quitting-why-doing-the-bare-minimum-at-work-Has-gone-global>
- Taylor, S. (2021, November 3). *The Psychology of Pandemics.* Journal of anxiety disorders. Retrieved December 11, 2022, from <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32078967/>
- United Nations. (2020). *Policy Brief: COVID-19 and the Need for Action on Mental Health.* Retrieved November 21, 2022, from [https://www.scirp.org/\(S\(351jmbntvnsjt1aadkposzje\)\)/reference/referencespapers.aspx?referenceid=2885230](https://www.scirp.org/(S(351jmbntvnsjt1aadkposzje))/reference/referencespapers.aspx?referenceid=2885230)
- United Nations International Labor Organization (ILO). (2020, January). *Decent work and youth in the Philippines.* International Labor Organization. Retrieved December 26, 2022, from https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---asia/---ro-bangkok/---ilo-manila/documents/publication/wcms_316218.pdf
- University of Cambridge . (n.d.). *Primary industry.* Cambridge Dictionary. Retrieved January 8, 2023, from <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/primary-industry>
- University of Oxford. (n.d.). *Secondary Industry.* Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary . Retrieved January 8, 2023, from <https://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com/us/definition/english/secondary-industry?q=secondary%2Bindustry>
- Urquhart, J. (2022, May 12). *Two in five employees have quit because of bad manager, study finds.* People Management. <https://www.peoplemanagement.co.uk/article/1755785/two-five-employees-quit-bad-manager-study-finds>
- Villarin, Demosthenes Jr. (2021, April 7). *85% of Philippine employers plan to use wellbeing program as Differentiator as workplace stress increases.* Willis Towers Watson. Retrieved

- November 27, 2022, from
<https://www.wtwco.com/en-PH/News/2021/04/85-percent-of-philippine-employers-plan-to-use-wellbeing-program-as-differentiator>
- Villegas, B. M. (2022, August 3). *Workforce skills critical IF Philippines is to gain from 'demographic dividend'*. BusinessWorld Online. Retrieved December 26, 2022, from
<https://www.bworldonline.com/economy/2022/08/03/465923/workforce-skills-critical-if-philippines-is-to-gain-from-demographic-dividend/#:~:text=According%20to%20the%20Philippine%20Statistics,36.25%25%2C%20in%20May%202022.>
- Weibo, S. (2021, June 3). *China's new 'Tang Ping' trend aims to highlight pressures of work culture*. BBC News. Retrieved November 26, 2022, from
<https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-china-57348406>
- West Visayas State University. (n.d.). *Ningas Cogon is an Attitude When We Start Something*. Course Hero. Retrieved November 30, 2022, from
<https://www.coursehero.com/file/109682013/Ningas-Cogon-is-an-attitude-when-we-start-somethindocx/>
- Wigert, B. (2022, March 1). *Employee burnout: The biggest myth*. Gallup. Retrieved November 8, 2022, from
<https://www.gallup.com/workplace/288539/employee-burnout-biggest-myth.aspx>
- Williams, A. (2022, September 20). *Tang Ping: How China's youth are refusing to work*. UnHerd. Retrieved November 28, 2022, from
<https://unherd.com/thepost/tang-ping-how-chinas-youth-are-refusing-to-work/>
- Yip, W. (2021, September 1). *China steps in to regulate brutal '996' work culture*. BBC News. Retrieved November 27, 2022, from
<https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-china-58381538>
- Zhang, L. M. (2022, September 28). *Singapore population grows 3.4% to 5.64m, reversing 2 consecutive years of decline*. The Straits Times. Retrieved December 26, 2022, from
<https://www.straitstimes.com/singapore/singapore-population-grows-34-to-564m-reversing-2-consecutive-years-of-decline>

VIII. APPENDIX

A. QUESTIONNAIRE

Demographics

Name:

Age:

Gender: (Male / Female / Non-Binary / Transgender / Prefer Not To Respond)

Area of Expertise/Occupation:

Industry:

Employment Type: (Full Time - Private / Full Time - Public / Freelance and Part-time / Contractual)

Years of Service with Present Company: (<1 year / 1-2 years / 3-5 years / 5-10 years / >10 years)

Years of Working Experience: (<1 year / 1-2 years / 3-5 years / 5-10 years / >10 years)

Salary Range per Month: (0-30,999 / 31,000-60,999 / 61,000-90,999 / 91,000-120,999 / 121,000-150,999 / 151,000 above)

Reward (External Driving Force)

1. I am willing to work beyond my job description even if I am not expecting a promotion.
2. I am willing to work beyond my job description even if there is no additional remuneration or reward like gift checks, additional leaves, etc.
3. I am willing to work beyond my job description even if my efforts are not recognized or noticed by the management.
4. I am willing to work even if the management is not willing to lessen my workload to accomplish the additional tasks they allocated to me.
5. If I can be on the same team with my close colleagues, I'm willing to work the extra mile.

Environment (External Driving Force)

1. I can multi-task and still work efficiently even after working hours.
2. I can freely express myself without any fear even when interacting with my managers.
3. I feel that the company cares about our professional development and welfare.
4. I feel like my colleagues inspire me to do better.
5. My managers are practicing fairness and accountability to create a secure working environment.

Fulfillment (Internal Driving Force)

1. I am doing a great job in my organization and it inspires me to be better.
2. I feel like I have contributed to the growth of the company.
3. I am fulfilled by helping my customers / clients by solving their problems and providing solutions.
4. I have found my purpose with my job and I am filled with joy going to work everyday.
5. I am enthusiastic and energized talking about work, doing it, and thinking about how I can contribute to the success of my organization.

Quiet Quitting Awareness Follow-up Questions

1. Do you always look forward to going out of the office on time? (Yes/No)
If yes, are you always on time going out? (Yes/No)
If not, what are the major factors of you extending working hours? (Please select)
 - Deadlines
 - Workload
 - Avoiding traffic jam/rush hour/extreme commuting
 - Chit-chat with colleagues
 - Additional pay (e.g. OT pay and incentives)
 - Others
2. Do you count the working days of the week and feel excited for Fridays and weekends? (E.g. Monday nanaman, ayoko pa mag-Monday, two days nalang friday na) (Yes/No)
3. Are you aware of quiet quitting? (Yes/No)
4. If yes, do you consider yourself a quiet quitter? (Yes/No)
5. If you consider yourself a quiet quitter, what factor(s) do you think made you become one?
 - Fatigue
 - Heavy workload
 - Unhealthy work environment
 - Limited opportunities
 - Poor communication
 - Undervalued and underappreciated
 - Underpaid
 - Stress and anxiety
 - Work-life balance realization
 - COVID-19 pandemic
 - Poor management
 - Burnout

- Outside work commitments and errands
- Others

B. SURVEY WEBSITE AND UX DESIGN

ATENEO DE MANILA UNIVERSITY
GRADUATE SCHOOL OF BUSINESS

Quiet Quitting Study Among Metro Manila Professionals

Good Day! We are students of the Ateneo de Manila University Graduate School of Business, conducting a study on quiet quitting. This study aims to determine the magnitude of quiet quitting among professionals in the National Capital Region (NCR) and to know the factors behind it. This will assist organizations in determining whether or not this is a national trend and how the factors identified in the findings will affect a firm's productivity.

Data Privacy Consent
In accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 and its Implementing Rules and Regulations, all of the information you provide will be treated with confidentiality and will only be used for academic research purposes. Your participation is purely voluntary, and you are entitled to ask that part, or all, of the record of your involvement in the survey be deleted or destroyed. In answering this questionnaire and disclosing personal information, you consent to the researchers accessing, collecting, and processing the information you provide solely for the purposes of this study.

Lux in Domino,
Jasmine Alberto
Mark Jason Badilla
Katrina Depacaquivo
Zyrah Marañon
Daniel Regaspi

- 1 Full Name
- 2 Age* [Done](#)
- 3 Gender*
- 4 Area of Expertise /Occupation*
E.g. Data Analysis, Market Intelligence, Civil Engineering, Land Surveying, Sales, etc.
- 5 Industry*

Other (Please Specify)
- 6 Employment Type*
- 7 Years of service with present company*

C. FIGURES

Gender Distribution of Respondents

Figure 1. Gender Distribution of Respondents

Respondents per Industry

Figure 2. Number of Respondents per Industry

Industry Groups Distribution

Figure 3. *Number of Respondents by Industry Group*

Respondent's Working Experience

Figure 4. *Number of Respondents by Working Experience*

Salary Range of the Respondents

Figure 5. *Number of Respondents by Salary Range*

Year of Service with Current Company

Figure 6. *Number of Respondents by Years of Service with Current Company*

Employment Type

Figure 7. *Number of Respondents by Employment Type*

Quiet Quitting Awareness of the Respondents

Figure 8. *Quiet Quitting Awareness of the Respondents*

Among the Aware Respondents, Who Considered Themselves as Quiet Quitters

Figure 9. *Among the Aware Respondents, Who Considered Themselves as Quiet Quitters*

Professionals Who Look Forward to Their Weekends / Day-Offs

Figure 10. *Percentage of Quiet Quitters Among Professionals Who Look Forward to Their Day-Offs*

Workers Who Look Forward to Leave Their Office On-Time

Figure 11. *Percentage of Quiet Quitters Among Workers Who Look Forward to Leave Their Office On-Time*

Factors that Made Respondents Stay Beyond Working Hours

Figure 12. *Factors that Made Respondents Stay Beyond Working Hours*

D. TABLES

<i>Domain Rewards</i>			<i>Domain Environment</i>		<i>Domain Self-Fulfillment</i>		<i>Overall</i>	
<i>Age</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
21-25	27	32.93%	3	17.65%	2	18.18%	3	30.00%
26-30	32	39.02%	7	41.18%	5	45.45%	5	50.00%
31-35	14	17.07%	4	23.53%	1	9.09%	2	20.00%
36-40	5	6.10%	1	5.88%	1	9.09%	0	0.00%
41-65 (up)	4	4.88%	2	11.76%	2	18.18%	0	0.00%
	82	100.00%	17	100.00%	11	100.00%	10	100.00%

Table 1. Percentage of Quiet Quitters per Domain by Age

<i>Domain Rewards</i>			<i>Domain Environment</i>		<i>Domain Self-Fulfillment</i>		<i>Overall</i>	
<i>Gender</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Female	51	62.20%	10	58.82%	6	66.67%	6	60.00%
Male	27	32.93%	5	29.41%	3	33.33%	3	30.00%
Non-binary/non-conforming	4	4.88%	2	11.76%	0	0.00%	1	10.00%
	82	100.00%	17	100.00%	9	100.00%	10	100.00%

Table 2. Percentage of Quiet Quitters per Domain by Gender

<i>Domain Rewards</i>			<i>Domain Environment</i>		<i>Domain Self-Fulfillment</i>		<i>Overall</i>	
<i>Salary Range</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
0-30,999	19	23.17%	5	29.41%	3	33.33%	2	20.00%
31,000-60,999	37	45.12%	7	41.18%	4	44.44%	3	30.00%
61,000-90,999	14	17.07%	2	11.76%	2	22.22%	3	30.00%
91,000-120,999	8	9.76%	2	11.76%	0	0.00%	1	10.00%
121,000-150,999	2	2.44%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
151,000 above	2	2.44%	1	5.88%	0	0.00%	1	10.00%
	82	100.00%	17	100.00%	9	100.00%	10	100.00%

Table 3. Percentage of Quiet Quitters per Domain by Salary Range

<i>Domain Rewards</i>			<i>Domain Environment</i>		<i>Domain Self-Fulfillment</i>		<i>Overall</i>	
<i>Years of working Experience</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
1-2 years	6	7.32%	1	5.88%	1	11.11%	0	0.00%
3-5 years	30	36.59%	3	17.65%	2	22.22%	2	20.00%
5-10 years	22	26.83%	6	35.29%	3	33.33%	5	50.00%
Less than 1 year	1	1.22%	1	5.88%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
More than 10 years	23	28.05%	6	35.29%	3	33.33%	3	30.00%
	82	100.00%	17	100.00%	9	100.00%	10	100.00%

Table 4. *Percentage of Quiet Quitters per Domain by Years of Working Experience*

<i>Domain Rewards</i>			<i>Domain Environment</i>		<i>Domain Self-Fulfillment</i>		<i>Overall</i>	
<i>Industry Group</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Primary	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
Secondary	6	7.32%	5	29.41%	1	11.11%	1	10.00%
Tertiary	52	63.41%	7	41.18%	5	55.56%	6	60.00%
Quaternary	24	29.27%	5	29.41%	3	33.33%	3	30.00%
	82	100.00%	17	100.00%	9	100.00%	10	100.00%

Table 5. *Percentage of Quiet Quitters per Domain by Industry Group*

Factors	Votes	Percentage
<i>Work-life balance realization</i>	164	38.50%
<i>Stress and Anxiety</i>	162	38.03%
<i>Underpaid</i>	154	36.15%
<i>Burnout</i>	146	34.27%
<i>Undervalued and unappreciated</i>	145	34.04%
<i>Fatigue</i>	143	33.57%
<i>Heavy workload</i>	132	30.99%
<i>Limited opportunities</i>	127	29.81%
<i>Unhealthy work environment</i>	122	28.64%
<i>Poor management</i>	116	27.23%
<i>Poor communication</i>	47	11.03%
<i>Outside work commitments and errands</i>	47	11.03%
<i>COVID-19 pandemic</i>	42	9.86%

Table 6. *Percentage of Chosen Factors Affecting Quiet Quitters*

Factors	Votes
Domain: Self-fulfillment	
<i>Work-life balance realization</i>	164
<i>Outside work commitments and errands</i>	47
Total Votes:	211
Domain: Environment	
<i>Stress and Anxiety</i>	162
<i>Burnout</i>	146
<i>Fatigue</i>	143
<i>Heavy workload</i>	132
<i>Unhealthy work environment</i>	122
<i>Poor management</i>	116
<i>Poor communication</i>	47
<i>COVID-19 pandemic</i>	42
Total Votes:	910
Domain: Reward	
<i>Underpaid</i>	154
<i>Undervalued and unappreciated</i>	145
<i>Limited opportunities</i>	127
Total Votes:	426

Table 7. *Categorized Factors by Domain of Self-fulfillment, Environment, and Reward*